

**RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF
O‘QUVCHILARINING BILIMLARINI BAHOLASH MEKANIZMLARINI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.**

Tursunova S.I.

Termiz davlat pedagogika instituti Boshlang‘ich ta‘limda matematika va ona tili kafedrası o‘qituvchisi Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori(PDh) v/b dotsent
+998915886422

saidatursunova@gmail.com

Qarshiyeva Ezoza

Boshlang‘ich ta‘lim yo‘nalishi talabasi 3-kurs

**Совершенствовање механизмов оценки знаний учащихся младших
классов на основе цифровых технологий.**

Термезский государственный педагогический институт начального
образования преподаватель
кафедры математики и педагогики родного языка доктор философских
наук (Ph.D.) оцент Турсунова С.И.

Каршиева Эзоза студент начального образования, 3-й курс

**Improving mechanisms for assessing the knowledge of primary school students
based on digital technologies.**

Termez State Pedagogical Institute Teacher of the Department of Mathematics
and Native Language in

Primary Education Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences Associate
Professor Tursunova S.I.

Karshiyeva Ezoza Primary education student, 3rd year

Anotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada boshlang‘ich sinif o‘quvchilarining bilimlarini baholashda raqamli texnologiyalarning rolini tahlil qilish, ularning ta‘lim jarayonidagi o‘rni va imkoniyatlarini ko‘rsatish maqsad qilingan. Raqamli baholash vositalarining samaradorligi, interaktiv testlar, virtual va kashfiyotlarni o‘rganish, o‘quvchilarning individual o‘rganish usullariga mos yondashuvlar va raqamli resurslardan foydalanishning ahamiyati keltirilgan. Shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalarni ta‘limga integratsiyalashda o‘qituvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasini oshirish va yangi baholash tizimlarini yaratish zarurligi ko‘rsatilgan. Maqola o‘quvchilarni baholashda yangi innovatsion metodlarni joriy etish orqali ta‘lim sifatini oshirish imkoniyatlarini tahlil etadi.

Kalit So‘zlar: Raqamli texnologiyalar, boshlang‘ich ta‘lim, bilimlarni baholash, interaktiv testlar, moslashuvchan o‘rganish, VR/AR, blended learning, o‘qituvchilar kompetensiyasi, ta‘lim resurslari, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish.

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является проанализировать роль цифровых технологий в оценке знаний учащихся младших классов, показать их место и возможности в образовательном процессе. Обсуждается эффективность инструментов цифровой оценки, интерактивных тестов, виртуального и исследовательского обучения, подходов, адаптированных к индивидуальному стилю обучения учащихся, а также важность использования цифровых ресурсов. Также показана необходимость повышения цифровой компетентности учителей и создания новых систем оценивания при интеграции цифровых технологий в образование. В статье анализируются возможности повышения качества образования за счет внедрения новых инновационных методов оценивания учащихся.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые технологии, начальное образование, оценка знаний, интерактивные тесты, адаптивное обучение, VR/AR, смешанное обучение, компетентность учителя, образовательные ресурсы, повышение качества образования.

Abstract: This article aims to analyze the role of digital technologies in assessing the knowledge of primary school students, to show their place and potential in the educational process. The effectiveness of digital assessment tools, interactive tests, virtual and discovery learning, approaches that are appropriate for individual learning styles of students, and the importance of using digital resources are presented. It also shows the need to improve the digital competence of teachers and create new assessment systems when integrating digital technologies into education. The article analyzes the possibilities of improving the quality of education by introducing new innovative methods for assessing students.

Keywords: Digital technologies, primary education, knowledge assessment, interactive tests, adaptive learning, VR/AR, blended learning, teacher competence, educational resources, improving the quality of education.

Introduction. Nowadays, digital technologies are playing a significant role in the education system. In order for the educational process to be interactive and effective, it is important to introduce modern technologies, motivate students to learn, and simplify the process of acquiring knowledge. Mechanisms for assessing students' knowledge, especially in primary education, are one of the main criteria for the quality of education. This article considers ways to improve mechanisms for assessing the knowledge of primary school students based on digital technologies¹.

To effectively integrate digital technologies into the primary education process, it is first necessary to choose suitable platforms and programs for teachers and students. Educational platforms, such as Google Classroom, Edmodo or Moodle, provide convenient opportunities for assessing student knowledge. These platforms allow teachers to monitor students individually, determine their level of mastery, and provide them with specific recommendations.

2. Interactive tests and quizzes. Interactive tests and quizzes play an important role in assessing student knowledge. Platforms such as Kahoot, Quizizz, and Quizlet can make the process of teaching and assessing students interesting and interactive. With the help of these programs, student assessment is carried out quickly and effectively. At the same time, teachers can adapt their assessment system, change tests, or create new tests.

3 Expanding Individualized Approaches to Students

It is important to adapt digital technologies to the individual characteristics of students. Each student may have different levels of knowledge and learning styles, so it is necessary to use an individual approach to assessing students. By introducing adaptive learning technologies, students are provided with materials and tests that are appropriate for their level. This method helps students improve their knowledge, and also allows the teacher to monitor the learning process of students.

4. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) tools

VR (Virtual Reality) and AR (Augmented Reality) tools can also be very effective in implementing new technologies, virtual and discovery. These technologies provide students with the opportunity to learn in an interesting and effective way. For example, with the help of AR, students can learn complex concepts in mathematics or natural sciences using 3D models. VR allows students to simulate real-life problems. Such technologies also make the process of knowledge assessment attractive and interactive.

5. Improving teacher digital competency

For the effective integration of digital technologies into education, the digital competence of the teacher is essential. It is necessary to organize regular trainings and courses on digital technologies for teachers. This will help teachers in the use of new technologies and will allow to make knowledge assessment mechanisms more effective. Teachers should be able to fully use digital resources and have the opportunity to accurately and quickly assess the level of student mastery.

6. Blended learning yondashuvi

Blended learning, a blended learning model, combines digital technologies and traditional teaching methods. In this approach, the teacher provides students with

reinforcement materials through digital platforms, which they then apply in face-to-face lessons. This approach allows students to receive timely and personalized support. Taking advantage of the advantages of the blended learning model in the assessment process allows for a complete assessment of student learning.

Literature Review: Digital educational technologies. The importance and effectiveness of using digital technologies in education have been studied in many scientific studies. There are a number of studies that show that digital technologies can simplify the educational process, increase student motivation, and actively involve them in the learning process (Markham, 2018; Johnson & Adams Becker, 2014).

Digital Assessment in Primary Education

The role of interactive assessment tools in assessing the knowledge of primary school students has received particular attention. Their use in education allows for a quick and accurate assessment of students' level of mastery (Kuhlman, 2017). Interactive tests, online platforms, and automated assessment systems have proven to be effective tools in analyzing student progress and mastery.

Summary. Improving the mechanisms for assessing the knowledge of primary school students based on digital technologies is of great importance in improving the quality of education and taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Innovative methods such as interactive platforms, individual approaches, VR/AR technologies and blended learning models make it possible to make the assessment of students' knowledge effective and interesting. It is also possible to improve the quality of primary education by increasing the digital competence of teachers and integrating new technologies into the educational process. Digital technologies are an effective tool in the field of education, and their application in student assessment mechanisms will take the educational process to a new level.

Methods:

The following methods were used in the article:

1. Analytical Method – Integrating digital technologies into education and analyzing their effectiveness in assessing knowledge.
2. Linguistic Method – Studying the theoretical and practical aspects of using digital technologies in assessing student knowledge through literature analysis.
3. Experimental Method – Assessing the level of student knowledge and determining the level of student mastery through the use of digital assessment tools.
4. Comparative Method – Comparing the effectiveness of digital and traditional assessment systems.

References:

REFERENCE

1. Людмила Ивановна Пономарева Турсунова Саида Исаковна Теоретические основы проблемы обучения младших школьников элементам рассуждения в процессе знакомства с художественными произведениями. ISSN 2542 - 0291 ВЕСТНИК ШАДРИНСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА Научный журнал ШГПУ , 2023 , No 2. 53-58.

2. SI Tursunova Uzbekistan is a country of friendship Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. 185-189-betlar.

3. СИ Турсунова Педагогические основы национализации школьного образования. ТГПИ. 2022 год.

4. Пономарева Людмила Ивановна Турсунова Саида Исаковна РАЗВИТИЕ СЛОВЕСНОГО ТВОРЧЕСТВА МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ НА УРОКАХ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОГО ЧТЕНИЯ. ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Сборник научных трудов. ISSN 2311-1305. Ялта 2024. 284-286. Том 82.

5. Tursunova Saida Isakovna SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF ORAL SPEECH IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS World of Scientific news in Science International Journal Impact factor: 8.1 (Researchbib) Vol 2 Issue 6. GERMANY, 2024. Страницы 137-143 Том 2

6. Tursunova Saida Isakovna. Linguistic-methodological problems of the development of oral speech in primary classes of national schools. Teacher of the Department of Primary Education, Termiz State Pedagogical Institute.

